

acetylcholine/cholinergic receptor (nAChR), nicotinic, $\beta 3$ (neuronal) (CHRNA3) : Machine learning discoveries of 2^{nd} order synergy in Meningiomas

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Abstract

Background : Nicotinic acetylcholine receptors (nAChRs), are polypeptides that form ligand-gated ion channels in the plasma membranes of certain neurons and on the pre/post-synaptic sides of the neuromuscular junction and respond to the neurotransmitter acetylcholine. CHRNA3 and CHRNA6 belong to this family and are located on 8p11. CHRNA6-CHRNA3 is a loci in nicotine dependence (ND)-related phenotypes. Further, CHRNA3 is implicated in epilepsies, nicotine dependence, alcohol behaviors, bipolar disorder, DSM-5 cocaine use disorder, Parkinson's disease, Duane retraction syndrome, chronic restraint stress, major depressive disorder, Retinal ganglion cells (RGCs) mechanisms and circadian clockwork. However, its role in meningiomas has not yet been determined completely. Meningiomas are the most common intracranial primary neoplasm in adults. Patel et al. [1] analyzed 160 tumors from all 3 World Health Organization (WHO) grades (I through III) using clinical, gene expression, and sequencing data and using unsupervised clustering analysis identified 3 molecular types (A, B, and C) that reliably predicted recurrence. Further, these groups did not directly correlate with the WHO grading system, which classifies more than half of the tumors in the most aggressive molecular type as benign. **Issue** : Increasing evidence point to the fact that meningioma classification and grading, that is based on histopathology does not always accurately predict tumor aggressiveness and recurrence behaviour and knowledge of the underlying biology of the treatment resistant meningiomas and the impact of genetic alterations in these tumors, is lacking. At the current stage more genomic studies are required to unravel the role of other genes and their interactions with other genetic factors. **Resolution** : In a recently published work Sinha [2], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. Adapting this search engine to the Meningioma dataset, i present here 2^{nd} order combinations of CHRNA3, some of which have been known to exist via wet lab experiments, but many are yet to be tested.

*ML dicoveries of CHRNA3 synergy in Meningiomas

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The reveals combinations might help oncologists/biologists test possible hypotheses that might be the causing factors in meningioma. Further, in my limited grasp, if proven true, the combinations revealed by the search engine might pave way for development of gene based therapies aimed at resolving pathological issues related to meningiomas.

Keywords: CHRNB3, Meningioma, Sensitivity analysis, Machine learning.

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1. Introduction

1.1. Meningioma

Meningiomas are the most common intracranial primary neoplasm in adults. They arise from the arachnoid cap cells. These arachnoid cap cells are specialized cells that make up the arachnoid mater (one of the three protective membranes covering the brain and spinal cord). The arachnoid mater is one of the three meninges. The other two that constitute the meninges are dura mater and pia mater.

1.1.1. World Health Organization (WHO) classification

The meningiomas are classified into three grades by WHO under the Central Nervous System tumours, namely, Grade I (benign), Grade II (atypical) and Grade III (anaplastic/malignant), based on histopathology or subtype (Louis et al. [3]). As of 2021, there exists 12 histopathological meningioma subtypes according to a mini-review by Torp et al. [4]. They are meningothelial, fibrous, transitional, psammomatous, angiomatous, microcystic, secretory, lymphoplasmacyte-rich, atypical, chordoid, clear cell and anaplastic (malignant) meningioma.

1.1.2. Historical perspective

Czarnetzki et al. [5] investigated a skull that was excavated at Steinheim/Murr (Baden-Württemberg, Germany) and consisted of a well preserved plagiocephalic cranium, with most of the facial skeleton intact. Their results of stratigraphical dating suggested the fossil specimen of *Homo steinheimensis*, was about 3,65,000 years old. In the fossile, they found that several features of the inner cranial table were consistent with a diagnosis of meningioma.

As documented in Okonkwo and Laws Jr [6], in 1614, Felix Plater, Professor of Medicine, issued a case report from the University of Basel on Caspar Bonecurtius, a noble knight stating -

began to lose his mind gradually over a two year period, to such an extent that finally he was completely stupefied and did nothing rationally. He had no desire for food and ate only when forcibly fed. ... Finally after matters had gone on thus for six months, he died.

Further, the autopsy report of Plater stated the following -

a round fleshy tumor, like an acorn. It was hard and full of holes and was as large as a medium-sized apple. It was covered with its own membrane and was entwined with veins. However, it was free of all connections with the matter of the brain, so much so that when it was removed by hand, it left behind a remarkable cavity.

This was the first case in the history that documented a patient with a lesion that was most compatible with a meningioma.

Next, in a contribution by Italian scientists, Paterniti [7] documents the first contribution of Andrea Vacca' Berlinghieri in 1813 in a manuscript *Trattato di Chirurgia Pratica*, which was never published. Its discovery was made accidentally by David Giordano, who referred in detail in an article on surgeon of Pisa in *La chirurgia di Andrea Vacca' Berlinghieri*. *Riv Storia Sci MedNat*. 1927: XVIII (3-4): 75-106. The unpublished manuscript of 488 pages describes that Vacca Berlinhieri proposed and performed a most bold radical operation. After a craniectomy with five or six burr holes on the outskirts of the fungus, the tumor was removed together the dura mater from which it originated, tying the cut vessels.

In 1847, Zanobi Pecchioli, Professor of Clinical Surgery and Operative Medicine at Modena and then at Siena University, published an account of surgeries performed during 16 years, from 1832 to 1847 (16 of the 1524 reported operations involved trephining

Figure 1: A schematic diagram of different pathways in different meningiomas, as provided by Szulzewsky et al. [12] under CC-BY Attribution 4.0 International license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

of the skull). In one of these interventions, he carried out on July 29 1835, in Siena, for the resection of a meningioma, a defined fungus of the duramater. The case was not referred in the literature by Pecchioli but was described by in Pecchioli [8]. Finally, Cushing [9] coined the modern term of "meningioma".

1.1.3. Pathophysiology

Meningiomas arise from arachnoidal cap cells, most of which are near the vicinity of the venous sinuses, and this is the site of greatest prevalence for meningioma formation. The dural venous sinuses (also called dural/cerebral/cranial sinuses) are venous sinuses (channels) found between the periosteal and meningeal layers of dura mater in the brain. They receive blood from the cerebral veins, and cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) from the subarachnoid space via arachnoid granulations. They mainly empty into the internal jugular vein. Cranial venous sinuses communicate with veins outside the skull through emissary veins. These communications help to keep the pressure of blood in the sinuses constant. (contributors [10] and Pamir et al. [11]) A schematic diagram for different pathways in different meningiomas has been provided in figure 1.

1.2. Nicotinic acetylcholine receptors (nAChRs)

Nicotinic acetylcholine receptors (nAChRs), are polypeptides that respond to the neurotransmitter acetylcholine. They are a part of the the cholinergic system belonging

to the autonomic nervous system which plays an important role in digestion, memory, blood pressure, control of heart beat, movement and many other functions (Tiwari et al. [13]). Acetylcholine (ACh) is an organic compound that functions in the brain and body of many types of animals (including humans) as a neurotransmitter (Sam and Bordoni [14]). Neurons secrete a signaling molecule, called a neurotransmitter to affect another cell across a synapse. Apart from operating as a neurotransmitter in various parts of the body, ACh most commonly associates with the neuromuscular junction. A neuromuscular junction is where motor neurons located in the ventral spinal cord synapse with muscles in the body to activate them. Further, ACh acts as a neurotransmitter in the autonomic nervous system, both as the neurotransmitter between preganglionic and postganglionic neurons and being the final release product from parasympathetic postganglionic neurons. ACh derives its name from its chemical structure, as it is an ester of acetic acid and choline. Parts in the body that use or are affected by acetylcholine are referred to as cholinergic.

nAChRs form ligand-gated ion channels in the plasma membranes of certain neurons and on the pre/post-synaptic sides of the neuromuscular junction. They, as ionotropic receptors, are directly linked to ion channels and do not use second messengers (as metabotropic receptors do). These receptors, have highly variable electrophysiological, kinetic and pharmacological properties and respond to nicotine differently, at different concentrations. It has also been discovered that various α and β subunit combinations could form functional nAChRs that could be activated by acetylcholine and nicotine. These combinations of subunits generate subtypes of nAChRs with diverse functional and pharmacological properties Graham et al. [15].

Nicotine dependence (ND), is a major public health challenge with multifactorial behavior, in which both genetic and environmental factors play a role. Brain nAChR-encoding genes are candidates studied in the context of ND, due of their biological relevance as binding sites for nicotine. Hitherto, most research on the role of nAChRs in ND has focused on two of these genes (encoding the $\alpha 4$ - and $\beta 2$ -subunits) and not much attention has been paid to the possible contribution of the other nine brain nAChR subunit genes ($\alpha 2\alpha 3$, $\alpha 5\alpha 7$, $\alpha 9\alpha 10$, $\beta 3\beta 4$) to the pathophysiology and genetics of ND. Greenbaum and Lerer [16] report that this situation has changed dramatically in which intensive research addressed the issue. Research has shown the importance of the CHRNA5-CHRNA3-CHRN3 and CHRNA6-CHRN3 loci in ND-related phenotypes. In their review, Greenbaum and Lerer [16] highlighted findings regarding the contribution of non- $\alpha 4/\beta 2$ -subunit containing nAChRs to ND.

1.3. acetylcholine/cholinergic receptor (nAChR), nicotinic, β 3 (neuronal) (CHRN3)

Anand and Lindstrom [17] determined the chromosomal location of 7 human neuronal nicotinic acetylcholine receptor subunit genes by genomic Southern analysis of hamster/human somatic cell hybrid DNAs. The following localizations were reported - β -2 subunit gene to human chromosome 1; α -2 and β -3 subunit genes to human chromosome 8; the α -3/5, and β -4 subunit genes to human chromosome 15; and the α -4 subunit gene to human chromosome 20.

Willoughby et al. [18] identified 3 cDNA clones homologous to rat neuronal nicotinic receptors in a human brain stem library by screening at low stringency with a mixture of rat α 5 and β -2/4 subunit probes. They found one positive clone that encoded a protein which exhibited characteristic features of a member of the ligand-gated ion channel class of protein subunits, and showed 89% homology with a rat β -3 neuronal nicotinic receptor subunit. They designated this clone the human β -3 neuronal nicotinic receptor subunit.

Koyama et al. [19] used an exon amplification method to construct a transcriptional map for human chromosome 8 and isolated transcribed sequences from defined regions of genomic DNA using cosmid clones. They further subcloned amplified fragments into a plasmid, pBluescriptII, and sequenced by the dideoxy chain termination method. Their sequence analysis to search for similarity or identity to known genes detected complete identity of one (ET634-2) of these exon amplification fragments, to the nucleotide sequence at 1138-1364 of the cDNA for the human nAChR [β]3 gene. This transcribed fragment, containing a part of the human nAChR [β]3 gene, was previously mapped to 8p11.2 by fluorescence in situ hybridization.

From brainstem, hippocampus, prefrontal cortex, substantia nigra, thalamus, and IMR32 libraries, Elliott et al. [20] isolated cDNA clones encoding human nAChR α -2/3/4/5/6/7, and β -2/3/4 subunits. They elicited inward currents by the application of acetylcholine (1-100 microM) and other agonists. They observed that these responses were blocked 65-97% by application of 10 microM d-tubocurarine, thus confirming functional expression of human nicotinic receptors.

Using PCR-based techniques, PJ and Luyten [21] isolated and sequenced the full-length cDNAs that encode the human neuronal nAChR subunits α -3/4/5/7 and β -2/3/4 in the neuroblastoma cell lines SH-SY5Y and/or IMR-32.

1.4. Roles of CHRN3 in different disease

Several loci/candidate genes for **epilepsies** or epileptic syndromes map or have been suggested to map to chromosome 8. Durner et al. [22] investigated families with adolescent-onset idiopathic generalized epilepsy (IGE), for linkage to markers spanning chromosome 8. Furtherm they studied juvenile myoclonic epilepsy (JME), epilepsy with only generalized tonic-clonic seizures occurring either randomly during the day (random grand mal) or on awakening (awakening grand mal), and juvenile absence epilepsy (JAE). They looked for a gene common to all these IGEs and found that the area where the LOD score reached the maximum, encompassed the location of the gene for the β -3-subunit of the nicotinic acetylcholine receptor (CHRN3). Thus this gene was a possible candidate for these specific forms of adolescent-onset IGE. Despite the health hazards, young women smoke cigarettes with high frequency. Greenbaum et al. [23] recruited 501 female Israeli students aged 20-30 years and obtained comprehensive background data and details of cigarette smoking and administered a battery of psychological instruments. They found nominally significant allelic and genotypic association with **smoking initiation** of single nucleotide polymorphism (SNP) rs2072660 and multilocus haplotypes in CHRN2 and nominal allelic or genotypic association of SNPs in CHRNA-7/9 (rs-1909884/4861065) and CHRN3 (rs9298629) with **nicotine dependence**.

Zeiger et al. [24] presented findings from an exploratory study of SNPs in the CHRN3 and CHRNA6 genes with tobacco and alcohol phenotypes, including frequency of use and 3 subjective response factors occurring shortly after initiation of use. They selected 1056 subjects ethnically diverse adolescents ascertained from clinical and community settings. They found most significant associations between two CHRN3 SNPs (rs4950 and rs13280604) and the 3 subjective response factors to initial tobacco use. Their findings were replicated in a separate community sample of 1524 families participating in the National Longitudinal Study of Adolescent Health. They found both CHRN3 SNPs to be associated with similar measures of subjective response to tobacco.

Though associated with nicotine dependence, Hoft et al. [25] presented evidence that CHRNA6 and CHRN3 genes, were associated with **alcohol behaviors**, using a nationally representative sample of adults. For this, they analysed 6 SNPs spanning the CHRN3/A6 genes using the statistical genetics software FBAT-PC and tested them using FBAT-PC including four alcohol phenotypes: average number of drinks, blackouts, total number of DSM-IV abuse and dependence symptoms endorsed, and quit attempts. They found association of 3 SNPs in CHRNA6 (i.e rs-1072003/892413/2304297) and one SNP in CHRN3 (rs13280604) with a composite of the alcohol phenotypes.

Due to the clinical relationship between **bipolar disorder** and nicotine dependence, Hartz et al. [26] investigated two research questions: • were genetic associations with nicotine dependence different in individuals with bipolar disorder as compared with individuals without bipolar disorder, and • did loci earlier associated with nicotine dependence had pleiotropic effects on these two diseases. For this, their study consisted of 916 cases with bipolar disorder and 1028 controls. In the investigation of pleiotropic effects of these SNPs on bipolar disorder, they found two highly correlated synonymous SNPs in CHRN3, rs-495/4953, were significantly associated with bipolar disorder. They observed that this association remained significant both after adjusting for a smoking covariate and analyzing the association in nonsmokers only.

Lee et al. [27] examined the association of SNPs of the CHRN3 (rs13280604) and CHRNA6 (rs892413) and symptoms of attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) in predicting smoking patterns from early adolescence to adulthood. For this, a longitudinal cohort of 1137 unrelated youths from the National Longitudinal Study of Adolescent Health was taken. They observed significant main effects of ADHD symptoms and CHRNA6 variants in predicting the number of cigarettes smoked and the pattern of use over time, respectively, with no main effects of the CHRN3 variants. However, they did observe a significant CHRN3 variant X-ADHD symptom interaction, such that individuals with elevated ADHD symptoms and a particular CHRN3 variant were at increased risk of cigarette use over time.

In the U.S.A., cocaine is the second most abused illicit drug. Using genotypic data from a GWAS of the Study of Addiction: Genetics and Environment (SAGE) dataset, Sadler et al. [28] tested the association of CHRN3-A6 SNPs with **DSM-5 cocaine use disorder**. They observed that multiple SNPs in the region were significantly associated with increased risk of cocaine use disorder. Their results suggested that the CHRN3-A6 locus contained multiple variants affecting risk for vulnerability to cocaine and nicotine dependence as well as bipolar disorder, suggesting that they have pleiotropic effects.

Cigarette smoking is protective in **Parkinson's disease** (PD), possibly due to nicotine action on brain nicotinic-acetylcholine receptors. CHRN3 is found to be depleted in the striatum of PD patients and associated with nicotine dependence. Bar-Shira et al. [29] sequenced the CHRN3 gene, and the c.-57G allele frequency was 0.31 and 0.26 among patients (n = 596) and controls (n = 369). Further, they found that the c.-57G allele was strongly associated with smoking in patients and the transcription factor Oct-1 binding was almost eliminated in lymphoblasts with the c.-57G/G genotype, and the CHRN3 promoter activity was reduced in cells with the c.-57G/G genotype. Their findings indicated that the CHRN3 c.-57A_ΔG alteration affected the promoter activity and was associated with PD and smoking in PD patients. Thus they hypothesized that nicotine might be valuable for patients who carry this alteration and beneficial in PD only for patients with specific genotypes.

In one patient, to evaluate possible monogenic and chromosomal anomalies with unilateral **Duane retraction syndrome** and modest dysmorphism, Abu-Amero et al. [30], used clinical evaluation, sequencing of candidate genes, and array comparative genomic hybridization (array CGH). They observed that the proband had unilateral Duane retraction syndrome (DRS) with low-set ears bilaterally, a high arched palate, and clinodactyly. Array CGH revealed a 16 Kb de novo deletion at chromosome 8p11.2 that encompassed a portion of only one gene, CHRN3. They concluded that the patient's chromosomal abnormality affected only one gene and could be related to her Duane retraction syndrome.

Dysfunction of cholinergic signaling in the brain has thought to be associated with depressive disorders. Han et al. [31] demonstrated that the expression levels of cholinergic signaling genes (CHAT, VACHT, CHT, CHRNA3, CHRN3-3/4) were down-regulated in a **chronic restraint stress** (CRS) rat model of depression, in which rats display depression-like behaviors such as anhedonia and mood despair. Further, to determine whether habenular cholinergic signaling was associated with regulation of dopamine neurons in the ventral tegmental area (VTA) and serotonin neurons in the dorsal raphe nucleus (DRN), they used CHAT::cre transgenic mice expressing the Designer Receptors Exclusively Activated by Designer Drugs (DREADD). They found that pharmacogenetic activation of habenular cholinergic neurons induced the excitation of dopamine neurons in the VTA and reduced the immunoreactivity of 5-hydroxytryptamine (5-HT) in the DRN. Also, habenular cholinergic gene down-regulation was recapitulated in the postmortem habenula of suicide victims diagnosed with **major depressive disorder** (MDD).

Retinal ganglion cells (RGCs) mechanisms make specific connections during development. Drayson and Triplett [32] characterized a RGC-specific Cre BAC transgenic line driven by elements of CHRN3. They showed that Cre expression was restricted to RGCs in the retina and sparsely expressed in the brain, importantly excluding retinorecipient regions. Further, they found that CHRN3-Cre mice labeled a wide variety of RGCs distributed throughout the retina and Cre activity was detected embryonically, shortly following RGC differentiation. Lastly, they found that CHRN3-Cre-labeled RGCs innervated multiple retinorecipient areas that serve both image-forming and nonimage forming functions.

The **circadian clockwork** is implicated in addiction, with circadian rhythm disruptions bidirectionally linked to substance abuse. Khan et al. [33] used machine learning

to reveal sex- and substance-specific associations with addiction in variants from 51 circadian-related genes (156,702 SNPs) in 98,800 participants from a UK Biobank cohort. They further analyzed SNP associations in a subset of the cohort for substance-specific addictions (alcohol, illicit drugs (narcotics), and prescription drugs (opioids)). They found robust and novel sex-specific and substance-specific associations with variants in ZBTB20, CHRNA3 and hormone receptors (RORA), particularly in individuals addicted to narcotics and opioids.

Many of the different synergies represented as combinations of genes/proteins have been experimentally tested and published. However, there are combinations that have yet to be explored. I address the problem of identifying these unexplored combinations via use of a machine learning based search engine in the next section.

1.5. Insight behind the work

Across all search engines has the fundamental principle remains the same i.e to capture the pattern available in the data and based on that pattern, rank a list of queries. Different algorithms can be applied, however if the fundamental pattern is captured accurately, then the rankings will remain approximately the same, with slight variations, across the different kinds of search engines used. I use one search engine, however, vary the way the patterns are captured via use of different sensitivity methods. Each sensitivity method uses a different flavour/mathematical formulation to compute the sensitivity indices to estimate the influence of the involved factors. These involved factors are genes that play a role in cell biology, in the above research. The insight is that all methods will capture the sensitivity of the involved factors based on their recorded regulations and the search engine will rank the combination of factors based on these sensitivity indices. Since the role of involved factors are captured properly, the search engine will give appropriate rankings to the combinations, thus capturing which gene combinations might be playing significantly in a biological phenomena. The above work shows rankings for experimentally confirmed combinations as well as unexplored/untested combinations. These rankings are not just numbers. They point to the existence of biological synergy in the form of gene combinations, whether tested in wet lab or unexplored till now. Finally, the findings suggest that the rankings are conserved across the different sensitivity methods used.

1.6. Combinatorial search problem and a possible solution

In a recently published work Sinha [2], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. The work uses SVM package by Joachims [34] in https://www.cs.cornell.edu/people/tj/svm_light/svm_rank.html. I use the adaptation to rank 2nd order gene combinations. The sensitivity package by Pujol et al. [35] was used to develop the search engine pipeline. The current research uses the Hilbert Schmidt Independence Criterion (HSIC) and SOBOL method, implemented in the sensitivity package mentioned above. I use three different kernels under the HSIC method namely, • laplace, • linear and • rbf. For SOBOL method, I use • sobol-2002, and • sobol-jansen. Each of these variants or kernels have been implemented in the sensitivity package and option

has been provided in the search engine code to generate the rankings for a particular gene, using a choice of a kernel/variant at a time. Technical details about the variants and kernels can be found in references cited in Pujol et al. [35].

2. Methods

2.1. Static data from Patel et al. [1]

Patel et al. [1] analyzed 160 meningioma samples from 140 patients, and according to the WHO histopathological classification system for meningioma, they found 121 tumors were of grade I (benign), 32 were of grade II (atypical), and 7 were of grade III (malignant). To determine whether meningiomas could be differentiated based on gene expression profiles, they used principal component analysis (PCA) on a discovery set of 97 tumors (i.e 77 WHO grade I and 20 WHO grade II). Next, they employed nonnegative matrix factorization (NMF) clustering (a unsupervised machine-learning approach) for $k = 2$ to $k = 7$ using the 1,500 genes that varied most among the tumor samples. They report that after 1,000 iterations, 3 clusters ($k = 3$) emerged as providing the best fit as determined by the consensus membership, cophenetic, and silhouette scores. They evaluated the cluster significance of the 3 subtypes using SigClust (Huang et al. [36]) and observed statistical significance between cluster boundaries, which exhibited significant differences in WHO grade representation.

2.2. Design for static data from Patel et al. [1]

The procedure begins with the listing of all C_k^n combinations for k number of genes from a total of n genes. Here n can be the choice of the biologist. k is ≥ 2 and $\leq (n - 1)$. Each of the combination of order k represent a unique set of interaction between the involved genetic factors. Since the sensitivity analysis methods require a sample for a particular observation, a steep gaussian distribution was generated with a jitter (noise) added to the deviation from the reported point measurement of 0.005. In this experiment, the distribution contained 10 measurements (including the point of measurement under consideration). This is repeated for each point of measurement.

To have an averaged ranking, the experiment was designed to run for 25 iterations. In each iteration, the datasets are combined in a specified format which go as input as per the requirement of a particular sensitivity analysis method. Thus for each p^{th} combination in C_k^n combinations, the dataset is prepared in a required format. Details of formatting the data have not been presented in the article to maintain the fluidity and brevity. Interested readers can find examples of formatting the data in the sensitivity analysis package in R. Sensitivity analysis and its relevance in systems biology have been covered in a recently published article by Sinha [37], which forms the foundation for this work. After the data has been transformed, vectorized programming is employed for density based sensitivity analysis and looping is employed for variance based sensitivity analysis to compute the required sensitivity indices for each of the p combinations.

After the above sensitivity indices have been stored for each of the p^{th} combination, for a chosen sensitivity analysis method, the next step in the design of experiment is conducted. Here, the indices are averaged per combination to have a mean index value. These index values form the discriminative features for a particular combination. For a k^{th} order combination, a vector of k elements or indices forms a feature vector. Thus for C_k^n combinations there will be C_k^n vectors, each containing k elements. Next, SVM_{learn}^{Rank} Joachims [34] is used to generate a model on default value C value of 20. In the current experiment on toy model C value has not been tuned. The training set helps in the generation of the model as the different gene combinations are numbered in order which are used as rank indices. The model is then used to generate score on the observations in the testing set using the $SVM_{classify}^{Rank}$ Joachims [34]. This is followed by sorting of these scores along with the rank indices already assigned to the gene combinations. The end result is a sorted order of the gene combinations based on the ranking score learned by the SVM^{Rank} algorithm.

Note that the following is the order in which the files should be executed in R Team [38], in order, for obtaining the desired results (Note that the code will not be explained here) - • use source("extractMeningiomadata.R") • use source("manuscript-2-2.R") • use source("SVMRank-Results-S-mean.R").

2.3. Translating the pipeline into code of execution in R

The execution begins by some preprocessing of the file containing the information regarding the down regulated genes via `source("extractMeningiomadata.R")`. The library containing the sensitivity analysis methods is then loaded in the interface using the command `library(sensitivity)` (Note - this package can be downloaded for free from <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/sensitivity/index.html>). Next a gaussian distribution for a particular transcript level for a gene is generated to have a sample. This is needed in the computation of sensitivity index for that particular gene. A gene of particular choice is selected (in blue) and the choice of the combination is made (here $k = 2$). Later a kernel is used (here rbf for HSIC method). 25 different indices are generated which help in generating aggregate rank using these 25 indices. The Support vector ranking algorithm is employed to generate the scores for different combinations and these scores are then sorted out. This is done using the command `source("SVMRank - Results - S - mean.R")`. A file is generated that contains the combinations in increasing order of influence. Note that 1 means lowest rank and vice versa, for 2^{nd} order combinations for any gene using a particular density based sensitivity index.

2.4. Regarding biological insight

For the recorded gene expression values, the sensitivity indices are computed. The search engine uses the kernel based density method. The kernel method takes the data, that is in a lower dimensional plane and projects it to a higher dimensional plane, with an idea that in a higher dimensional place, there exists a dot product between the projected data. To simply state, the idea is that in a higher dimensional plane the nonlinearities between the data (in lower dimensional plane) will be captured and the data

may be segregated from each other via a hyperplane. So, irrespective of the method used to measure the gene expression values, if the measurements capture biological information (to whatever extent they can), then the kernel method will be able to capture the nonlinearities/synergies, if existing and allow the sensitivity analysis method (here density based method) to estimate the strength of influence of each of the factors. Based on the sensitivity indices of combinations of a particular order, the search engine ranks the combinations. Details of search engine are provided in the published work in Sinha [2].

It is important to note that the search engine will not give insight about the mechanism of synergy between the components of a combination. However, if the synergy exists between components of an unexplored/untested combination, then the sensitivity indices will capture the influence of these components taken together (which form a combination of interest) and will rank the combination appropriately. These rankings provide insight about which combination a biologist/oncologist might want to test in a forest of combinations for a given scenario in a cell (whether normal or pathological).

3. Results & Discussion

3.1. CHRNB3 related synergies

Note - CHRNB3 was found to be upregulated in Type B. Upregulation was defined as Type logFC to be > 1 and $FDR \leq 0.001$, in Patel et al. [1]. Also, sorting of scores by the machine learning algorithm were done in ascending order, i.e - top is lowest in ranking. A total of 392 2^{nd} order combinations of CHRNB3 were recorded.

3.1.1. CHRNB3 - individual genes

The following genes in combination with CHRNB3 showed high rankings - solute carrier family 12 member 1 (SLC12A1), sushi repeat containing protein X-linked (SRPX), proprotein convertase subtilisin/kexin type 1 inhibitor (PCSK1N), GLI family zinc finger 1 (GLI1), natriuretic peptide receptor 3 (NPR3), solute carrier family 30 member 3 (SLC30A3), lysosomal associated membrane protein family member 5 (LAMP5), kinesin family member 1A (KIF1A), podocan like 1 (PODNL1), peripherin (PRPH), sodium voltage-gated channel alpha subunit 7 (SCN7A), luteinizing hormone/choriogonadotropin receptor (LHCGR), dual oxidase 2 (DUOX2), NKD inhibitor of WNT signaling pathway 1 (NKD1), reticulocalbin 3 (RCN3), neurexophilin 2 (NXPH2), ADAM metallopeptidase domain 12 (ADAM12), fasciculation and elongation protein zeta 1 (FEZ1), mohawk homeobox (MKX), AT-rich interaction domain 5B (ARID5B), serine protease 23 (PRSS23), cysteine rich transmembrane BMP regulator 1 (CRIM1), enkurin, TRPC channel interacting protein (ENKUR), thyroid hormone receptor beta (THRB), ADAM metallopeptidase with thrombospondin type 1 motif 12 (ADAMTS12), VENT homeobox (VENTX), potassium voltage-gated channel subfamily E regulatory subunit 4 (KCNE4), dimethylarginine dimethylaminohydrolase 1 (DDAH1), roundabout guidance receptor 3 (ROBO3), ABI family member 3 binding protein (ABI3BP), chromosome 10 open reading frame 90 (C10orf90), matrix metallopeptidase 16 (MMP16),

tetraspanin 7 (TSPAN7), protein phosphatase 2 regulatory subunit Bbeta (PPP2R2B), sushi domain containing 3 (SUSD3), myosin IE (MYO1E), exostosin like glycosyltransferase 1 (EXTL1), SLAM family member 8 (SLAMF8), RUNX family transcription factor 1 (RUNX1), meiosis 1 associated protein (MIAP), trichohyalin (TCHH), coiled-coil-helix-coiled-coil-helix domain containing 6 (CHCHD6), collagen type XXVI alpha 1 chain (COL26A1), sialic acid binding Ig like lectin 11 (SIGLEC11), sialic acid binding Ig like lectin 16 (gene/pseudogene) (SIGLEC16), LDL receptor related protein 5 (LRP5), ELAV like RNA binding protein 4 (ELAVL4), matrix remodeling associated 8 (MXRA8), NLR family pyrin domain containing 3 (NLRP3), coiled-coil domain containing 74A (CCDC74A), NK6 homeobox 1 (NKX6-1), amyloid beta precursor protein binding family B member 2 (APBB2), 15-hydroxyprostaglandin dehydrogenase (HPGD), coagulation factor II thrombin receptor like 2 (F2RL2), EBF transcription factor 1 (EBF1), transmembrane protein 200A (TMEM200A), dishevelled binding antagonist of beta catenin 2 (DACT2), myozenin 3 (MYOZ3), collagen type I alpha 2 chain (COL1A2), somatomedin B and thrombospondin type 1 domain containing (SBSPON), carbonic anhydrase 3 (CA3), transmembrane protein 71 (TMEM71), sushi, von Willebrand factor type A, EGF and pentraxin domain containing 1 (SVEP1), heat shock protein family A (Hsp70) member 12A (HSPA12A), HtrA serine peptidase 1 (HTRA1), microfibril associated protein 4 (MFAP4), trans-golgi network vesicle protein 23 homolog A (TVP23A), lactate dehydrogenase D (LDHD), proline rich transmembrane protein 2 (PRRT2), cytochrome P450 family 2 subfamily S member 1 (CYP2S1), 5'-nucleotidase domain containing 2 (NT5DC2), filamin A interacting protein 1 like (FILIP1L), RAB31, member RAS oncogene family (RAB31), nephronectin (NPNT), atonal bHLH transcription factor 8 (ATOH8), vesicle associated membrane protein 5 (VAMP5), energy homeostasis associated (ENHO), armadillo repeat containing 4 (ARMC4 / ODAD2), carnitine palmitoyltransferase 1C (CPT1C), coiled-coil domain containing 126 (CCDC126), G protein-coupled receptor 183 (GPR183), integrin subunit alpha M (ITGAM), G protein-coupled receptor 27 (GPR27), microtubule associated protein 6 (MAP6), mono-ADP ribosylhydrolase 2 (MACROD2), StAR related lipid transfer domain containing 5 (STARD5), interleukin 17D (IL17D), pseudopodium enriched atypical kinase 1 (PEAK1), sushi domain containing 5 (SUSD5), heart development protein with EGF like domains 1 (HEG1), homeobox B2 (HOXB2), CD248 molecule (CD248), dynein axonemal heavy chain 12 (DNAH12), purinergic receptor P2Y14 (P2RY14), yippee like 2 (YPEL2), family with sequence similarity 131 member A (FAM131A), calcium binding protein 4 (CABP4), solute carrier organic anion transporter family member 3A1 (SLCO3A1), BCL2 family apoptosis regulator BOK (BOK), MEF2 activating motif and SAP domain containing transcriptional regulator (MAMSTR), frizzled class receptor 8 (FZD8), myozenin 1 (MYOZ1), phosphodiesterase 4D interacting protein (PDE4DIP), cysteine and serine rich nuclear protein 3 (CSRNP3), class II major histocompatibility complex transactivator (CIITA), potassium voltage-gated channel subfamily E regulatory subunit 1 (KCNE1), NME/NM23 family member 9 (NME9), PLAG1 zinc finger (PLAG1), exostosin glycosyltransferase 1 (EXT1), biglycan (BGN), EPH receptor B3 (EPHB3), phospholipase C beta 1 (PLCB1), neurotrimin (NTM), regulator of G protein signaling 6 (RGS6), pyrroline-5-carboxylate reductase 1 (PYCR1), nebulin (NEB), family with sequence similarity 43 member B (FAM43B), olfactomedin like 1 (OLFML1), dual specificity

phosphatase 5 pseudogene 1 (DUSP5P1), adrenoceptor alpha 2C (ADRA2C), protein kinase D1 (PRKD1), colony stimulating factor 1 (CSF1), fibronectin leucine rich transmembrane protein 2 (FLRT2), protein kinase cGMP-dependent 1 (PRKG1), SHC adaptor protein 4 (SHC4), cytochrome P450 family 4 subfamily Z member 1 (CYP4Z1), cytochrome P450 family 4 subfamily X member 1 (CYP4X1), reticulon 4 receptor like 2 (RTN4RL2), A-kinase anchoring protein 19 (C2orf88 / AKAP19), kelch repeat and BTB domain containing 12 (KBTBD12), low density lipoprotein receptor class A domain containing 2 (LDLRAD2), ectonucleoside triphosphate diphosphohydrolase 8 (ENTPD8), nuclear GTPase, germinal center associated (NUGGC), serine/threonine kinase 31 (STK31), dishevelled binding antagonist of beta catenin 3 (DACT3), adenosine deaminase RNA specific B1 (ADARB1), sialophorin (SPN), chromosome 2 open reading frame 27A (C2orf27A / LINC03124), C-type lectin domain containing 9A (CLEC9A), DLG associated protein 2 (DLGAP2), metallothionein 1F (MT1F), integrin subunit beta like 1 (ITGBL1), delta like canonical Notch ligand 1 (DLL1), ryanodine receptor 3 (RYR3), dual specificity phosphatase 29 (DUSP27 / DUSP29), RNA, U6 small nuclear 529, pseudogene (RNU6-529P), phospholipid phosphatase 4 (PLPP4), synaptotagmin 15 (SYT15), family with sequence similarity 155 member A (FAM155A), transmembrane protein 240 (TMEM240), 3-hydroxyacyl-CoA dehydratase 2 (HACD2), glutathione peroxidase 3 (GPX3), high mobility group box 3 pseudogene 7 (HMGB3P7), RFPL1 antisense RNA 1 (RFPL1S), long intergenic non-protein coding RNA 937 (LINC00937), long intergenic non-protein coding RNA 1907 (LINC01907), ITGB2 antisense RNA 1 (ITGB2-AS1), LMCD1 antisense RNA 1 (LMCD1-AS1), zinc finger protein 883 (ZNF883) and sorting nexin 18 pseudogene 13 (SNX18P13).

Using the adaptation of the above mentioned search engine, I tabulate the rankings of 2nd order combination of CHRN3 with the above list, that were reported to be upregulated in Patel et al. [1]. Table 1 and 2 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 3 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 1 and 2.

One can also interpret the results of the table 1 and 2 graphically, with the following influences - • Individual members w.r.t CHRN3 with CHRN3 – > SLC12A1 / SRPX / PCSK1N / GLI1 / NPR3 / SLC30A3 / LAMP5 / KIF1A / PODNL1 / PRPH / SCN7A / LHCGR / DUOX2 / NKD1 / RCN3 / NXPH2 / ADAM12 / FEZ1 / MKX / ARID5B / PRSS23 / CRIM1 / ENKUR / THRB / ADAMTS12 / VENTX / KCNE4 / DDAH1 / ROBO3 / ABI3BP / C10orf90 / MMP16 / TSPAN7 / PPP2R2B / SUSD3 / MYO1E / EXTL1 / SLAMF8 / RUNX1 / M1AP / TCHH / CHCHD6 / COL26A1 / SIGLEC11 / SIGLEC16 / LRP5 / ELAVL4 / MXRA8 / NLRP3 / CCDC74A / NKX6-1 / APBB2 / HPGD / F2RL2 / EBF1 / TMEM200A / DACT2 / MYOZ3 / COL1A2 / SBSPON / CA3 / TMEM71 / SVEP1 / HSPA12A / HTRA1 / MFAP4 / TVP23A / LDHD / PRRT2 / CYP2S1 / NT5DC2 / FILIP1L / RAB31 / NPNT / ATOH8 / VAMP5 / ENHO / ARMC4 / CPT1C / CCDC126 / GPR183 / ITGAM / GPR27 / MAP6 / MACROD2 / STARD5 / IL17D / PEAK1 / SUSD5 / HEG1 / HOXB2 / CD248 / DNAH12 / P2RY14 / YPEL2 / FAM131A / CABP4 / SLCO3A1 / BOK / MAMSTR / FZD8 / MYOZ1 / PDE4DIP / CSRNP3 / CIITA / KCNE1 / NME9 / PLAG1 / EXT1 / BGN / EPHB3 / PLCB1 / NTM / RGS6 / PYCR1 / NEB / FAM43B / OLFML1 / DUSP5P1 / ADRA2C / PRKD1 / CSF1 / FLRT2 / PRKG1 / SHC4 / CYP4Z1 /

RANKING INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS CHRNB3									
RANKING OF INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T CHRNB3									
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen		laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
SLC12A1 - CHRNB3	218	248	230	379	SRPX - CHRNB3	221	201	275	43
PCSK1N - CHRNB3	23	192	244	370	GLI1 - CHRNB3	216	76	225	354
NPR3 - CHRNB3	134	234	211	390	SLC30A3 - CHRNB3	245	228	219	2
LAMP5 - CHRNB3	271	330	283	86	KIF1A - CHRNB3	232	214	247	5
PODNL1 - CHRNB3	237	113	207	374	PRPH - CHRNB3	191	191	228	386
SCN7A - CHRNB3	15	217	253	389	LHCGR - CHRNB3	217	206	180	371
DUOX2 - CHRNB3	231	204	163	291	NKD1 - CHRNB3	274	227	215	373
RCN3 - CHRNB3	248	159	203	322	NXPH2 - CHRNB3	153	242	295	369
ADAM12 - CHRNB3	343	278	300	157	FEZ1 - CHRNB3	223	257	241	311
MKX - CHRNB3	287	269	245	78	ARID5B - CHRNB3	293	381	392	329
PRSS23 - CHRNB3	326	329	330	74	CRIM1 - CHRNB3	294	280	321	128
ENKUR - CHRNB3	331	282	339	133	THRB - CHRNB3	297	270	287	61
ADAMTS12 - CHRNB3	243	322	229	324	VENTX - CHRNB3	306	235	266	296
KCNE4 - CHRNB3	353	359	348	213	DDAH1 - CHRNB3	386	384	347	232
ROBO3 - CHRNB3	247	296	357	102	ABI3BP - CHRNB3	129	281	250	328
C10orf90 - CHRNB3	322	253	279	227	MMP16 - CHRNB3	275	316	342	192
TSPAN7 - CHRNB3	351	347	249	53	PPP2R2B - CHRNB3	225	181	209	337
SUSD3 - CHRNB3	391	390	353	114	MYO1E - CHRNB3	334	369	344	256
EXTL1 - CHRNB3	281	294	277	346	SLAMF8 - CHRNB3	388	391	310	158
RUNX1 - CHRNB3	309	383	386	249	MIAP - CHRNB3	390	336	332	167
TCHH - CHRNB3	377	371	381	140	CHCHD6 - CHRNB3	371	365	333	261
COL26A1 - CHRNB3	233	134	206	391	SIGLEC11 - CHRNB3	350	283	388	205
SIGLEC16 - CHRNB3	365	289	385	206	LRP5 - CHRNB3	325	312	345	207
ELAVL4 - CHRNB3	339	258	343	126	MXRA8 - CHRNB3	352	315	370	219
NLRP3 - CHRNB3	348	362	314	306	CCDC74A - CHRNB3	160	285	361	275
NKX6-1 - CHRNB3	273	321	260	98	APBB2 - CHRNB3	312	351	329	300
HPGD - CHRNB3	316	244	299	355	F2RL2 - CHRNB3	267	238	246	24
EBF1 - CHRNB3	253	297	336	359	TMEM200A - CHRNB3	346	302	358	199
DACT2 - CHRNB3	303	317	262	283	MYOZ3 - CHRNB3	310	295	296	340
COL1A2 - CHRNB3	368	299	315	269	S BSPON - CHRNB3	266	231	274	55
CA3 - CHRNB3	246	163	217	381	TMEM71 - CHRNB3	318	392	263	233
SVEP1 - CHRNB3	270	260	312	70	HSPA12A - CHRNB3	244	220	221	253
HTRA1 - CHRNB3	276	298	355	210	MFAP4 - CHRNB3	254	268	267	110
TVP23A - CHRNB3	301	380	346	121	LDHD - CHRNB3	286	386	368	234
PRRT2 - CHRNB3	319	286	290	108	CYP2S1 - CHRNB3	382	335	351	228
NT5DC2 - CHRNB3	384	338	391	77	FILIP1L - CHRNB3	290	339	320	118
RAB31 - CHRNB3	314	353	366	356	NPNT - CHRNB3	369	284	375	208
ATOH8 - CHRNB3	376	388	376	220	VAMP5 - CHRNB3	298	363	363	241
ENHO - CHRNB3	257	346	268	326	ARMC4 - CHRNB3	263	240	285	87
CPT1C - CHRNB3	264	308	220	36	CCDC126 - CHRNB3	269	382	354	190

Table 1: 2nd order interaction ranking between CHRNB3 VS Individual members.

CYP4X1 / RTN4RL2 / C2orf88 / KBTBD12 / LDLRAD2 / ENTPD8 / NUGGC / STK31 / DACT3 / ADARB1 / SPN / C2orf27A / CLEC9A / DLGAP2 / MT1F / ITGBL1 / DLL1 / RYR3 / DUSP27 / RNU6-529P / PLPP4 / SYT15 / FAM155A / TMEM240 / HACD2 / GPX3 / HMGB3P7 / RFPL1S / LINC00937 / LINC01907 / ITGB2-AS1 / LMCD1-AS1 / ZNF883 / SNX18P13.

4. Conclusion

Presented here are a range of multiple synergistic CHRNB3 2nd order combinations that were ranked via a machine learning based search engine. Via majority voting across the ranking methods, it was possible to find plausible unexplored synergistic

RANKING INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS CHRNB3									
RANKING OF INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T CHRNB3									
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen		laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
GPR183 - CHRNB3	300	332	390	155	ITGAM - CHRNB3	327	376	316	276
GPR27 - CHRNB3	324	341	212	262	MAP6 - CHRNB3	392	313	356	101
MACROD2 - CHRNB3	383	348	337	235	STARD5 - CHRNB3	299	222	254	83
IL17D - CHRNB3	329	366	304	200	PEAK1 - CHRNB3	321	355	306	119
SUSD5 - CHRNB3	292	236	298	285	HEG1 - CHRNB3	363	357	252	286
HOXB2 - CHRNB3	317	328	269	332	CD248 - CHRNB3	335	255	273	242
DNAH12 - CHRNB3	241	279	242	32	P2RY14 - CHRNB3	328	259	338	280
YPEL2 - CHRNB3	354	264	378	168	FAM131A - CHRNB3	296	246	331	236
CABP4 - CHRNB3	288	293	276	76	SLCO3A1 - CHRNB3	291	261	328	290
BOK - CHRNB3	358	356	289	271	MAMSTR - CHRNB3	307	354	302	99
FZD8 - CHRNB3	345	350	365	187	MYOZ1 - CHRNB3	333	265	278	347
PDE4DIP - CHRNB3	355	344	297	171	CSRN3 - CHRNB3	315	370	371	188
CIITA - CHRNB3	311	307	379	176	KCNE1 - CHRNB3	366	324	308	221
NME9 - CHRNB3	338	305	350	301	PLAG1 - CHRNB3	380	379	367	156
EXT1 - CHRNB3	362	263	325	162	BGN - CHRNB3	347	311	309	237
EPHB3 - CHRNB3	360	368	382	201	PLCB1 - CHRNB3	228	225	270	239
NTM - CHRNB3	214	232	239	10	RGS6 - CHRNB3	224	67	259	378
PYCR1 - CHRNB3	379	361	364	222	NEB - CHRNB3	304	358	243	263
FAM43B - CHRNB3	285	306	294	104	OLFML1 - CHRNB3	302	275	303	64
DUSP5P1 - CHRNB3	277	364	286	345	ADRA2C - CHRNB3	272	245	233	272
PRKD1 - CHRNB3	344	288	284	344	CSF1 - CHRNB3	372	300	234	209
FLRT2 - CHRNB3	381	309	293	316	PRKG1 - CHRNB3	349	337	271	250
SHC4 - CHRNB3	278	256	265	84	CYP4Z1 - CHRNB3	367	387	360	90
CYP4X1 - CHRNB3	385	349	384	302	RTN4RL2 - CHRNB3	313	360	372	180
C2orf88 - CHRNB3	373	367	373	223	KBTBD12 - CHRNB3	234	343	313	323
LDLRAD2 - CHRNB3	337	229	235	292	ENTPD8 - CHRNB3	259	340	258	342
NUGGC - CHRNB3	215	333	387	270	STK31 - CHRNB3	370	326	305	174
DACT3 - CHRNB3	357	287	349	303	ADARB1 - CHRNB3	378	373	301	238
SPN - CHRNB3	289	378	377	169	C2orf27A - CHRNB3	330	389	380	184
CLEC9A - CHRNB3	154	223	251	309	DLGAP2 - CHRNB3	308	277	183	372
MT1F - CHRNB3	374	291	317	317	ITGBL1 - CHRNB3	336	276	389	173
DLL1 - CHRNB3	242	314	307	294	RYR3 - CHRNB3	265	239	226	57
DUSP27 - CHRNB3	361	352	352	191	RNU6-529P - CHRNB3	356	331	326	318
PLPP4 - CHRNB3	230	247	214	164	SYT15 - CHRNB3	359	320	282	81
FAM155A - CHRNB3	261	237	236	89	TMEM240 - CHRNB3	260	345	322	59
HACD2 - CHRNB3	342	385	374	159	GPX3 - CHRNB3	158	249	256	331
HMGB3P7 - CHRNB3	282	219	264	314	RFPL1S - CHRNB3	340	273	319	129
LINC00937 - CHRNB3	323	292	318	224	LINC01907 - CHRNB3	389	250	383	170
ITGB2-AS1 - CHRNB3	239	290	369	96	LMCD1-AS1 - CHRNB3	226	342	288	181
ZNF883 - CHRNB3	295	377	362	193	SNX18P13 - CHRNB3	256	267	237	149

Table 2: 2nd order interaction ranking between CHRNB3 VS Individual members.

combinations of CHRNB3-X that might be prevalent in meningioma.

Conflict of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

Author's contributions

Concept, design, in silico implementation - SS. Analysis and interpretation of results - SS. Manuscript writing - SS. Manuscript revision - SS. Approval of manuscript - SS

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES

Individual members w.r.t CHRN3	
SLC12A1 / SRPX / PCSK1N / GLI1 / NPR3 ...	
SLC30A3 / LAMP5 / KIF1A / PODNL1 / PRPH ...	
SCN7A / LHCGR / DUOX2 / NKD1 / RCN3 / NXPH2 ...	
ADAM12 / FEZ1 / MKX / ARID5B / PRSS23 / CRIM1 ...	
ENKUR / THRB / ADAMTS12 / VENTX / KCNE4 ...	
DDAH1 / ROBO3 / ABI3BP / C10orf90 / MMP16 ...	
TSPAN7 / PPP2R2B / SUSD3 / MYO1E / EXTL1 ...	
SLAMF8 / RUNX1 / MIAP / TCHH / CHCHD6 / COL26A1 ...	
SIGLEC11 / SIGLEC16 / LRP5 / ELAVL4 / MXRA8 ...	
NLRP3 / CCDC74A / NKX6-1 / APBB2 / HPGD ...	
F2RL2 / EBF1 / TMEM200A / DACT2 / MYOZ3 ...	
COL1A2 / SBSPON / CA3 / TMEM71 / SVEP1 ...	
HSPA12A / HTRA1 / MFAP4 / TVP23A / LDHD ...	
PRRT2 / CYP2S1 / NT5DC2 / FILIP1L / RAB31 ...	
NPNT / ATOH8 / VAMP5 / ENHO / ARMC4 / CPT1C ...	
CCDC126 / GPR183 / ITGAM / GPR27 / MAP6 ...	
MACROD2 / STARD5 / IL17D / PEAK1 / SUSD5 ...	
HEG1 / HOXB2 / CD248 / DNAH12 / P2RY14 / YPEL2 ...	
FAM131A / CABP4 / SLCO3A1 / BOK / MAMSTR / FZD8 ...	
MYOZ1 / PDE4DIP / CSRNP3 / CIITA / KCNE1 / NME9 ...	
PLAG1 / EXT1 / BGN / EPHB3 / PLCB1 / NTM / RGS6 ...	
PYCR1 / NEB / FAM43B / OLFML1 / DUSP5P1 / ADRA2C ...	
PRKD1 / CSF1 / FLRT2 / PRKG1 / SHC4 / CYP4Z1 ...	
CYP4X1 / RTN4RL2 / C2orf88 / KBTBD12 / LDLRAD2 ...	
/ ENTPD8 / NUGGC / STK31 / DACT3 / ADARB1 / SPN ...	
C2orf27A / CLEC9A / DLGAP2 / MT1F / ITGBL1 / DLL1 ...	
RYR3 / DUSP27 / RNU6-529P / PLPP4 / SYT15 / FAM155A ...	
TMEM240 / HACD2 / GPX3 / HMGB3P7 / RFPL1S / LINC00937 ...	
LINC01907 / ITGB2-AS1 / LMCD1-AS1 / ZNF883 / SNX18P13	CHRN3

Table 3: 2^m order combinatorial hypotheses between CHRN3 and Individual members.

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Source of Data

Data used in this research work was released in a publication in Patel et al. [1]. Permission to use, granted by PNAS.

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